

Potentiometric Studies on Ternary Metal Complexes of some Aliphatic Acids and Amino Acids

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Manuscript received 16 October 1995, accepted 15 February 1996

The formation of mixed-ligand complexes by titration of metal ions and two competing ligands has attracted attention concerning their structure and stability. Furthermore, due to the important application of aliphatic acid derivatives and amino acids much attention has been paid to the binary metal complexes of these compounds¹. However, little work has been reported on the ternary metal complexes involving the two competing ligands, aliphatic acids and amino acids².

The present communication reports a systematic study on the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and some aliphatic acids (succinic acid, malic acid and tartaric acid as primary ligands) and/or amino acids (glycine, alanine, aspartic acid as secondary ligands) using potentiometric titration technique. This study is concerned with the formation and stability of the ternary complexes in relation to that of the binary ones.

Results and Discussion

Representative titration curves are shown in Fig. 1 of various M²⁺-H₂L-a.a systems. It is evident that the various 1 : 1 binary ML complexes are formed at low pHs (3.5–4.0). This is achieved from the observed divergence of 1 : 1 binary M²⁺-aliphatic acid titration curve (e) from that of the corresponding free acid solution (curve d). It is worthy to indicate that different binary metal complex solutions of aliphatic acids (H₂L-M²⁺) show a precipitate at pH > 6. On the other hand, the titration curves (b and c) reveal that different M²⁺-a.a binary complexes begin to form in the pH range 3–6 depending on the nature of the a.a moiety used with each metal ion.

The titration curves of the different 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes are strongly overlapped with the corresponding ones of 1 : 1 binary M²⁺-H₂L complex at lower pH values (Fig. 1). This behaviour suggests that the amino acid does not combine with the metal ion at low pHs. Generally above certain pH values depending on the nature of both the primary aliphatic acid (H₂L) as well as metal ion, a divergence of the ternary titration curve from that the corresponding binary ML titration curve is observed (curves t, e). This shows the coordination of amino acid anion with the binary ML complex in stepwise manner as represented by the following equation :

where, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}.

In this respect, it is worthy to mention that the binary

ML complexes are quite stable up to the pH range 4.0–6.0, where the attachment of the amino acid takes place forming the ternary complexes [ML(a.a)]. Thus it may be assumed that amino acid anion would combine with [ML] binary in ternary systems as it does with [M(H₂O)_x]²⁺ in a binary system. From the titration curves (Fig. 1) the horizontal distance between curves (e) and (f) was used for the calculation of n_{mix} (average number of the secondary ligand a.a) associated with one [ML] using the equation³,

$$\bar{n}_{\text{mix}} = \frac{(V_f - V_e) [\Gamma^{n+} E + T_L (y - \bar{n}_H)]}{(V_o + V_e) \bar{n}_H T_M^o}$$

where Γ_M^o is the concentration of [ML] which is equal to the concentration of M²⁺ used, y the number of dissociable protons of amino acid (y = 1 and 2 for mono- and dicarboxylic amino acids respectively), V_o the original volume of the titrated solution (50 ml), V_e, V_f are the volume of alkali consumed at the same pH values in curves (e) and (f) respectively. All other symbols have their usual meaning³ n_H for the secondary ligand, amino acid at different pH values were available from determination of the proton-amino acid formation constant values as described later. From the obtained n_H values, free secondary ligand exponent (PL_{mix}) was calculated using the equation,

$$\text{PL}_{\text{mix}}^- = \log_e \left[\frac{\sum_{y=0}^{1 \text{ or } 2} \beta_Y^H \left(\frac{1}{10B} \right)^y \cdot \frac{V_o + V_e}{V_o}}{T_L^o - \bar{n}_{\text{mix}} T_M^o} \right]$$

where β_Y^H is the second and third formation constant values for the applying a.a, β the pH- meter reading and T_L^o the concentration of the second ligand a.a. The second dissociation constant values for all amino acids studied as well as the third dissociation constant values of aspartic acid were determined from the titration curves (a) and (b) making use of the Irving and Rossotti formulation³. The obtained values are in good agreement with the literature values⁴. It is worth mentioning that the first dissociation constant values of all the amino acids are too low (~2.0) occurring in strongly acidic media. Accordingly, these values are not used in the calculations. The dissociation constants of the various aliphatic acids were evaluated from the

titration curves (a) and (d). The values obtained are found to cope much with those reported in the literature⁵.

Formation curves corresponding to the various 1 : 1 : 1 ($M^{2+} : H_2L : a.a$) ternary complex systems were obtained by plotting n_{mix} vs pL_{mix} . The corresponding formation

constants $\log K_{ML}^{M(H_2L)}$ obtained by the average value

method are listed in Table 1. For comparison of the stability of the ML(a.a) ternary system studied with that of the binary ML or M(a.a), the formation constants of the different binary systems were determined. This was made by applying the original equations of Irving and Rossotti³ to

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT VALUES FOR THE BINARY $M(II)-H_2L$, $M(II)-a.a$ AND THE MIXED-LIGAND $M(II)-H_2L-a.a$ COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaNO_3$)

Ligand	M			M(succ.)			M(mal.)			M(tar.)		
	$\log K_{M(H_2L \text{ or } a.a)}$			$\log K_{M(succ. (a.a))}$			$\log K_{M(mal. (a.a))}$			$\log K_{M(tar. (a.a))}$		
	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
Succ. acid	6.10	6.54	6.75									
Malic acid	5.65	5.75	6.10									
Tar. acid	5.22	5.54	5.50									
Glycine	5.20	5.77	8.00	4.80	5.55	7.85	4.40	5.20	7.25	4.45	5.00	7.35
Alanine	4.85	5.75	6.90	4.75	5.65	6.78	4.65	4.95	6.45	4.15	4.75	6.20
Leucine	4.80	5.70	7.20	4.35	5.41	6.20	4.11	4.82	5.92	3.79	4.55	5.10
Asp. acid	7.00	7.35	8.50	6.86	7.21	8.10	6.10	6.97	7.90	5.95	6.82	8.10

a.a = Amino acid.

the binary complex solution systems (Fig. 1) curves (b), (c) and (d), (e) $M^{2+}-a.a$ and $M^{2+}-H_2L$ respectively. It is worthy to indicate that no precipitation occurred at pH lower than at which $\bar{n}$ (average number of H_2L or a.a molecules bound to metal ion) equals 0.5, confirming that hydrolysis of the formed complexes does not likely interfere in the calculation of the stability constants of these binary complexes. The various $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{ML}^M(a.a)$ values obtained from the experimental formation curves $\bar{n}$ vs pL plots (where pL is the free H_2L or a.a exponent) of the binary complex system by the average value and straight-line methods are reported in Table 1. The data reveal that the stability of the formed 1 : 1 : 1 ($M^{2+}-H_2L-a.a$) ternary complexes is lower than that of the corresponding 1 : 1 $M^{2+}-a.a$ binary complexes. This behaviour is expected where the binary ML complexes has fewer site available for bonding than that to the latter ones. Moreover, in the association of the amino acid with the aquated $[M(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$, there is coulombic attraction between the positive charge on the latter

Fig. 1. Titration curves for ($CO^{2+} + \text{succinic acid} + \text{alanine}$) as 25° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaNO_3$) with $0.098 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ $NaOH$.

and the negative charge on the anion of the former one, facilitating the formation of the binary $M(a.a)$ complex, i.e. high formation constant. Further, comparison of the formation constant values for the same M^{2+} binary or ternary complex in terms of nature of the secondary ligand monocarboxylic amino acid moiety reveals that the stability of the formed complexes runs almost according to the sequence : glycine > alanine > leucine. This behaviour can be interpreted in terms of the basicities of the amino acid, i.e. their affinity to act as σ -donor as well as the steric effects. Generally, increasing the length of the amino acid alkyl chain (R) would result in more strain on its bonding, i.e. relatively low stability. Furthermore, for the dicarboxylic amino acid (asp. acid) it is observed that the formation constant of the binary or ternary complex containing this ligand is much higher than that of the corresponding one containing monocarboxylic amino acid. This can be ascribed to the effective high basicity of the α, β -dicarboxylic (asp. acid, $pK_{a2} = 13.86$) relative to that of monocarboxylic amino acids studied ($pK_{a2} = 9.21-9.78$)⁴ as well as the high tendency of asp. acid to act as ONO tridentate ligand forming five- and six-membered chelate rings. On the other hand, the formation constant of the formed bi-

nary or ternary of the same metal ion complexes in terms of nature of primary ligand dicarboxylic aliphatic acids decreases in the following order : succinate ion ($pK_{a1} = 4.21$, $pK_{a2} = 5.64$) > malate ion ($pK_{a1} = 3.40$, $pK_{a2} = 5.06$) > tartrate ion ($pK_{a1} = 3.04$, $pK_{a2} = 4.3$). This trend can be ascribed to the decrease in basicity of the conjugate bases of these acids in the same direction, i.e. a decrease in σ -donor ability along the same sequence. With respect to the metal ions and for all complexes studied, the stability is in the sequence : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ which is in harmony with the Irving-Williams order⁷.

Experimental

Analytical grade (Merck/B.D.H.) $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, aliphatic acids (succinic, malic, tartaric), amino acids (gly, ala, leuc, asp acid) were used. Standard solutions (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) of aliphatic (H_2L) and amino acids (a.a) were prepared in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. The base (NaOH) used for titration and KH-phthalate employed in the standardisation of NaOH as well as HNO_3 and NaNO_3 were of analytical grade.

Potentiometric titrations : Titrations with a relatively highly concentrated standard carbonate-free NaOH solutions of different M^{2+} - H_2L and/or a.a mixture in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio ($5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of each) were carried out at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Ionic strength and total volume were kept constant at 0.1 mol dm^{-3} (NaNO_3) and 50 ml respectively. pH-metric measurement was performed on an Orion 501 pH-meter with a glass electrode assembly. The solution ions were titrated according to the following scheme : (a) HNO_3 , (b) $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{a.a}$, (c) $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{a.a} + \text{M}^{2+}$, (d) $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{L}$, (e) $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{L} + \text{M}^{2+}$ and (f) $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{L} + \text{M}^{2+} + \text{a.a}$.

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